

1 Handling Bounded Log Sizes

Logically, logs are append-only storages to which we can continuously append. Practically, we are bounded by the physical storage of our devices. Therefore, we can not record an unbounded number of versions of our data types. In this section, we describe how we can safely retain the last K versions of our data type by removing old entries from OpLog. We make two underlying assumptions: (i) our physical storage has the capacity to store more than K versions and (ii) the replicas merge among themselves at a rate such that there is at least one version common at the top of the OpLogs among all replicas before any replica runs out of space.

The major challenge in keeping a history of at least the last K versions is that this set of last K versions is constantly changing. The order of operations in the global history changes with updates from different replicas. So instead, we identify versions that we know for certain are not in the set of last K versions.

Consider an arbitrary version vs . Referring back to how our *insert* operation (cf. Section 6 in the paper) works, we know vs in the OpLog of a reader can be pushed down in order due to a merge step involving an unknown operation that the reader has not seen before. This essentially means that even if vs was not in the set of last K versions, it may become so. However, if all replicas in our system have observed all the same operations from the start up to vs , we know the positions of those versions will not change.

This means that a replica X_i can safely remove n operations from the top of its OpLog while preserving at least the last K versions if: (i) all the other replicas in the system have those n operations in the top n entries of their respective OpLogs and (ii) the replica has already seen at least K more new operations after those n operations. Note that X_i need not check whether the other replicas have received K more new operations to trim its own OpLog. It just has to make sure there is a set of operations from the top that all the replicas have executed in the same order. This trimming operation can be triggered after a user-defined number ($> K$) of versions have been recorded. However, if this number is near K , trimming will be frequent and may adversely affect system performance.

A replica X_i need not scan the top of each replica's OpLog to find the entries that can be trimmed. Instead, it consults the tails of KnowledgeLogs. For each node ID $s \in S$, X_i reads the tails of the N KnowledgeLogs $K_u^s (u \in S)$ and identifies the smallest version stamp. We denote this set of N versions as C . Then C contains one version vs for each originator X_s such that vs is the greatest version with node ID s that all the replicas have seen.

Next, X_i locates the earliest sequence number in its log where such a version is present. Let this sequence number be seq . Note that any version in an entry preceding the entry at seq in $OpLog(X_i)$ must be present in all the other replicas. Therefore, X_i can trim all the entries up to seq provided that there are at least K versions following it. If not, it can backtrack the required number of entries to meet this condition and then proceed with trimming.

There are some caveats to this approach that we must overcome. First, although the earliest n versions trimmed in this approach are not part of the latest K versions, we may still need the last version of the earliest n versions as an anchor point for future *insert* operations. This can happen if there is at least one replica such that it had exactly n versions at the time X_i trimmed its OpLog. Hence, we must record the last version in the set of trimmed versions every time we perform this operation. We can safely overwrite this record every time we trim the log.

Second, the mappings in KnowledgeLogs will be off by n whenever n operations are trimmed. To counter this, we introduce *Virtual Sequence Numbers (VSN)*. VSN of an entry in a log represents the sequence number the entry would have if the log was never trimmed. Therefore, we must track an *offset* (initially zero) that is updated every time we trim an OpLog from the top (incremented by the number of entries trimmed). Then to get the VSN of an entry, we can simply add its sequence number to the offset. KnowledgeLogs now store VSNs instead of sequence numbers. While trimming the OpLog, we can trim the corresponding KnowledgeLog entries as well. Just like OpLogs, we track the last entry removed from a KnowledgeLog to notify the readers of the trimmed operations.

Third, if a new replica joins the cluster with an initially empty state, it can force a change in the order of operations. This can be overcome in two ways: we can copy the initial state of the new replica from an arbitrary existing replica, or we can assign an ID to the new replica that is smaller than all the existing replicas. A smaller ID will force the new replica to put its entries at the end of all the existing versions and thus, not alter the current order.

2 Eventually Consistent IoT Applications

1. Smart lock [1]
2. Energy management [2]
3. Temperature prediction [3]
4. Intrusion detection [4]
5. Charging pile management for electric vehicles [4]

References

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